

ICCM22, Melbourne, Australia

Investigation on Ni-Mn-Ga particles/Cu composites prepared by powder metallurgy method

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ICCM22
MELBOURNE
AUSTRALIA

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

哈爾濱工程大學

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Outline

1. Introduction
2. Experimental procedure
3. Results and discussion
4. Summary

Introduction

Magnetic Shape
Memory Alloys
(MMSAs)

Single crystalline alloy → High MFIS, but difficult preparation, high cost

Polycrystalline alloy → Easy preparation, very brittle

Introduction

To take advantage of the merits and avoid demerits of these alloys

NiMnGa alloy particles/polymer composites have been proposed and developed

J. Feuchtwanger (J. Appl. Phys. 97 (2005) 10M319, J. Appl. Phys. 93 (2003) 8528–8530)

In the previous literatures, it was reported that the NiMnGa particles/polymer composites exhibit a large energy absorption due to the martensitic twin boundary motion of Ni-Mn-Ga. However, the mechanical property of the composites was not high due to the use of polymer matrix.

In comparison with polymer, metal should have a high strength and good interfacial bonding with the NiMnGa particles. Mg has been employed to composite with NiMnGa particles (*Mater. Sci. Eng. A 615 (2014) 273-277*).

Introduction

Cu has a large plasticity but low mechanical strength, which can be strengthened by compositing with hard particles. In the present work, Cu has been used to be matrix to composite with Ni-Mn-Ga particles by powder metallurgical method. Microstructure, phase transformation and mechanical property of the composites are systematically investigated.

Experimental Procedure

$\text{Ni}_{49.8}\text{Mn}_{28.5}\text{Ga}_{21.7}$ particles with content of 40, 50 and 60 wt%

+

Cu powder

Mixed by ball mill, and compacted under $\sim 770\text{MPa}$

Sintering at 1173K

Composites

Results and discussion

Fig. 1 Optical micrograph of sintered samples, (a) Cu, (b) 40%, (b) 50%, and (b) 60% composites

Results and discussion

Fig. 2 SEM image of sintered samples, (a) Cu, (b) 40%, (b) 50%, and (b) 60% composites

Results and discussion

Fig. 3 Susceptibility-temperature curves of NiMnGa particles and composites

Results and discussion

Fig. 4 XRD patterns of Ni-Mn-Ga particles, Cu powder and composites.

Results and discussion

Fig. 5 Compressive stress-strain curves of Ni-Mn-Ga bulk, sintered Cu and composites

Results and discussion

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 6 SEM image of fracture surface for (a) 40%, (b) 50% and (c) 60% composites

Summary

1. The Ni-Mn-Ga particles/Cu composites have been prepared by pressureless sintering method.
2. Ni-Mn-Ga particles are mainly distributed around the grain boundaries of Cu matrix. With increasing Ni-Mn-Ga particles content, the grain size of Cu matrix is gradually decreased.
3. The phase transformation of Ni-Mn-Ga particles is decreased after compositing with Cu matrix. With increasing Ni-Mn-Ga particles content, the Curie transition of composites is gradually enhanced.
4. The composites have better mechanical properties than the pure Ni-Mn-Ga or Cu.

Thanks for your attention!

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